

Marie Curie

Data management plan required?	Yes, however: Grant holder must comply with CR-UK's policy on data sharing and preservation by ensuring they submit a data management plan. Refer to CR-UK's policy.
RDM policy Link	Refer to CR-UK's policy
Definition of data	Refer to CR-UK's policy
Length of data management plan	Refer to CR-UK's policy
DMP template/ requirements	Refer to CR-UK's policy
Required data repository	Refer to CR-UK's policy
Time for data release	Refer to CR-UK's policy
Time for long-term storage of data	Refer to CR-UK's policy
Costings	Refer to CR-UK's policy
Last updated	Refer to CR-UK's policy
Contact Details	research.grants@mariecurie.org.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

Marie Curie Research Grants Terms and Conditions

<https://www.mariecurie.org.uk/globalassets/media/documents/research/funding-for-research/marie-curie-research-programme/marie-curie-research-grants-terms-and-conditions.pdf> (see 14.1.3 Data Sharing and Preservation Policy on management and sharing of data arising from Cancer Research UK funded research.)

Accessed: May 2018